

QTAB Data Use Agreement

Last updated: 24th February 2023

Introduction

This Data Use Agreement (DUA) outlines the terms and conditions for requesting access to the Queensland Twin Adolescent Brain (QTAB) dataset. Researchers accessing human subjects' data, and their research institution, are responsible for maintaining the privacy of those subjects and the confidentiality of their data. By signing and submitting this QTAB DUA, you and your institution are accepting the terms and conditions for responsibly using human subjects' data. Read the entire DUA carefully before signing and submitting this agreement. Ensure that all members of your research team who will have access to the data under this DUA (Recipients) have also read the DUA and have agreed to abide by the terms of the DUA. You and your institution are responsible for the way that all listed Recipients use the data. Failure to adhere to the terms and conditions of this DUA could result in denial of further access to QTAB data and in other actions.

The QTAB Dataset

The QTAB dataset contains human subjects' research data stored across multiple research data repositories. Imaging data are openly shared through the OpenNeuro platform (<https://openneuro.org>). Genotypic data will be shared through a specialised genotypic data repository from 2023. All available non-imaging phenotypic and demographic data are shared through the Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org>) as a restricted access dataset (henceforth referred to as the QTAB Zenodo dataset). Shared QTAB data have been stripped of all individual identifiers. However, the unique and intrinsically personal nature of behavioural data, genomics data, brain imaging data, and other derivative data included in these repositories, combined with new analytical methodologies and decreasing computing and storage costs, has altered the framework through which "identify-ability" can be defined. To protect and assure the confidentiality and privacy of all participants, all Recipients who are granted access to these data are expected to adhere to all terms of use outlined in this DUA.

Access Request Overview

The QTAB Project team will approve access to data from the QTAB Zenodo dataset for research purposes only. The QTAB Project team will review the Access Request and the proposed DUA of each Recipient requesting data and determine whether to provide access based on the expectations outlined in the following pages. These expectations include the protection of data privacy, confidentiality, and security. In the event that requests raise particular concerns related to privacy and confidentiality, risks to populations or groups, or other concerns, the QTAB Project team will consult with other experts as appropriate. The QTAB Project team reserves the right to suspend or revoke approved Access Requests at any time if concerns arise regarding the appropriateness of data usage by Recipient or Recipient's compliance with the DUA.

Recipients seeking access to data from the QTAB Project are expected to submit their DUA, certified and co-signed by the Lead Investigator and the designated Institutional Official. Completing the DUA is a necessary step to access data from the QTAB Zenodo dataset.

Steps to Access the QTAB Zenodo Dataset

1. Request access to the dataset through the Zenodo platform
2. Read the QTAB Data Use Agreement (DUA), sign the Recipient Information and Certifications section and obtain your Authorised Institutional Official's approval and signature.
3. Submit the completed DUA to Dr Lachlan Strike (lachlan.strike@qimrberghofer.edu.au). By submitting an individual's name on the form, you and your Institutional Official affirm that the collaborators have read and agreed to the terms and conditions within the DUA. Your collaborators at different organizations must complete separate requests for the data.
4. Access Request Review: Requests to access the QTAB Zenodo dataset will be reviewed to ensure completeness of the application and scientific appropriateness of the intended project.
5. After review and approval, the user will receive notification that access has been granted to the requested QTAB Zenodo dataset.

Data Use Terms and Conditions

I request access to the QTAB Zenodo dataset, for the purpose of scientific investigation, scholarship or teaching, or other forms of research and research development as described in the following QTAB Data Use Agreement (DUA). I, and any Other Recipients listed in this DUA, agree to the following terms:

1. Scope of Work

A Standard Scope of Work that covers most anticipated uses of the data is provided in the Recipient Information and Certifications section (page 7).

- a. Any data obtained under this DUA will be used by Recipient solely in connection with the “Scope of Work” submitted with the Access Request and for no other purpose.
- b. Recipient agrees that any data obtained under this DUA will not be used in any research that is not within the approved Scope of Work.

2. Non-transferability of Agreement

This DUA is not transferable. Recipients must notify Professor Katie McMahon (k21.mcmahon@qut.edu.au) or Dr Lachlan Strike (lachlan.strike@qimrberghofer.edu.au) of changes in institutional affiliation. Recipients who change institutional affiliation will be removed from the DUA and they must submit a new DUA from their new institution to retain access. If the Lead Recipient changes institutions, they may identify another Recipient on the DUA as a replacement.

3. Data for Research Use

Recipients agree to use data for scientific investigation, scholarship or teaching, or other form of research and research development. Generally, data will be used by the Recipient in connection with the purpose indicated and described in the *Research Data Use Statement* in the *Recipient Information and Certifications* below. Recipients are encouraged to explore shared, *broadly consented* data in the QTAB dataset for a variety of purposes including secondary analysis, hypothesis generation, and replication regardless of whether said exploration leads to analysis in support of a question beyond the scope of the originally identified purpose described in the *Research Data Use Statement*.

4. No Distribution of Data

Recipients agree to retain control over data and to not distribute, sell, or move data, with or without charge, in any form, to any other individual, entity, or third-party system except to authorized collaborators as specified below. This includes raw data from any individual participant and derived subject-level data if the derived data can aid in the re-identification of a research participant. There may be some judgement concerning whether derived data can aid in the re-identification of a research participant. Any questions concerning this issue should be directed to the Recipient’s Institutional Review Board (IRB) or Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC).

5. Collaboration with Shared Data

Recipients may distribute (share) data from the QTAB Zenodo dataset with authorized researchers (collaborators) who are listed on their Institutional ethics approval for the same Permission Group and have agreed to the terms in this DUA, for the purpose of collaboration on research projects only. Recipients are responsible for ensuring that collaborators are authorized researchers. If the DUA has expired, it must be renewed prior to sharing data.

6. No Re-identification of Subjects

Recipients agree that data will not be used to attempt to establish the individual identities of any of the study participants from whom data were obtained (or their relatives) and/or contact the individual study participant, except as permitted by law (e.g., in connection with a separately

negotiated collaboration with the original research team or the enrolment of the consented subject in the Recipient's study). Recipients agree to notify Professor Katie McMahon (k21.mcmahon@qut.edu.au) or Dr Lachlan Strike (lachlan.strike@qimrberghofer.edu.au) as soon as possible if, upon use of QTAB data, identifying information is discovered. Recipients agree to not publish or distribute any derived data that could aid in the re-identification of any of the study participants (or their relatives). Any questions concerning this issue should be directed to the Recipient's IRB or HREC.

7. Compliance with Applicable Human Subjects Protection and Institutional Requirements

Recipients agree to comply with all applicable rules for the protection of human subjects. Recipients are responsible for determining whether their proposed research with data from the QTAB Zenodo dataset necessitates consultation with their IRB or HREC. Recipients must consider any psychological, social, economic, and other potentially harmful impacts their research results could have on individuals, communities, and society, and take steps to minimize them. Recipients agree to report promptly to their IRB or HREC any unanticipated problems involving risks to subjects or others. This DUA is made in addition to, and does not supersede, any of Recipient's institutional policies or any local, State, and/or Federal laws and regulations that provide additional protections for human subjects. Recipients acknowledge that access, if provided, is for research that is approved by the institution with which they are affiliated.

8. Security

Recipients agree to protect data from the QTAB dataset by implementing the controls needed to maintain the confidentiality integrity, and availability of the data. By signing this agreement, Recipients acknowledge that they have implemented a security plan to prevent data loss or breach, whether the data are stored on local machines or with a cloud service provider. Recipients agree that the data will be protected in a manner consistent with security best practices which include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Accounts and passwords are not shared.
- Data are protected from anonymous access and are never exposed to the internet.
- Data are protected using standard encryption protocols and/or strong password protection.
- Software patches are kept up to date.

9. Deletion of Data

Recipients agree that data that has been downloaded from the QTAB Zenodo dataset will be permanently deleted from all local or cloud-based machines when research is completed or this DUA is expired, whichever comes first. If research data must be retained at the end of a project (e.g., to comply with a Code of Conduct), the data must be stored in a secure repository, with only those listed on the Institutional ethics application(s) able to access to the data.

10. Acknowledgements

Recipients agree to acknowledge the QTAB Zenodo dataset and the relevant Digital Object Identifier(s) (DOI), in any and all oral and written presentations, disclosures, and publications (including abstracts, as space allows) resulting from any and all analyses of data. Oral or written presentations, disclosures, or publications should include the appropriate acknowledgement statement(s).

11. Data Disclaimers

Recipients acknowledge that the QTAB project does not and cannot warrant the results that may be obtained by using any data or data analysis tools included in the QTAB Zenodo dataset. The QTAB project team disclaims all warranties as to the accuracy of the data in the QTAB Zenodo repository or the performance or fitness of the data or data analysis tools for any particular purpose.

12. Recipients' Permission to Post Information Publicly

Recipients agree to permit The University of Queensland, the Queensland University of Technology, and the QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute to publicly summarize the Recipients' research use of data along with the Recipients' name and organizational/institutional affiliation, as listed in this DUA.

13. Non-Endorsement

Recipients agree not to claim or imply endorsement by the QTAB project team or The University of Queensland of (a) the project or projects being conducted under the Research Data Use Statement, or (b) the Recipient Parties or any other entities or personnel related to or involved in the project(s).

QTAB Data Recipient Information and Certifications

1. Research Data Use Statement

Research Project (title):

Standard Scope of Work: Exploration of behavioural associations in a genetically informative dataset, including associations with brain imaging, genomic, and biological measures.

By signing and dating this DUA as part of requesting access to the QTAB Zenodo dataset, my Institutional Official and I certify that Recipient will abide by the DUA. We further acknowledge that the Recipient Investigator has shared this document and the QTAB policies and procedures with any research staff who will participate in the use of QTAB data. My Institutional Official(s) also certifies that they have shared this document and the relevant QTAB policies and procedures with appropriate institutional entities and individuals.

2. Recipient/Lead Recipient

First Name: _____ Last Name: _____ Degree: _____

Institution: _____

City: _____ State/Province: _____ Country: _____

Phone: _____ Email: _____

3. Authorised Institutional Official

Name: _____

Position: _____

Email Address: _____

4. Signatures

By signing and dating this DUA to request access to data in the QTAB Zenodo repository, I and my Institutional Official certify that we will abide by the Data Use Terms and Conditions defined in this DUA. I further acknowledge that I have shared this document with any Other Recipients who will participate in the use of data from the QTAB Zenodo repository. My Institutional Official also acknowledges that they have shared this document with appropriate institutional organizations.

Lead Recipient Signature

Date

Authorised Institutional Official Signature

Date

**Inquiries and completed Data Usage Agreements should be sent to Dr Lachlan Strike
(lachlan.strike@qimrberghofer.edu.au)**